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A study of Emotional Intelligence of Bachelor of Education (B.Ed.) students of Aurangabad City. Dr. Baig Muntajeeb Ali & M.M. Baig.

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A Study of Emotional Intelligence of Bachelor of Education(B.Ed) Students of Aurangabad City

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Abstract :

The present study tries to study the Emotional Intelligence of B.Ed Students of Aurangabad City, Maharashtra, India. The data was collected through Survey Method. Two B.Ed colleges were selected at random; out of each college fifty students (25 boys & 25 Girls) were selected at random, to make the Sample Size of 100. Roqan Emotional Intelligence Test was used to collect data. It has thirty items covering five dimensions viz. Self Awareness, Self Regulation, Motivation, Empathy and Social Skills. The data collected was given statistical treatment using Mean and Standard Deviation and t-test. The study revealed that the Emotional Intelligence of B.Ed Students is Normal and there is significant difference in Emotional Intelligence of male and female B.Ed Students.

Introduction :

Emotion is a very complex phenomenon. Emotions not only influence our behavior but also control our living, Social adjustment and development of personality. Emotions may be defined as a stirred up state of the organism (Dash and Dash, p91). Arthur T Jerschild says "emotions" denotes a state being moved, stirred up or aroused in some way (as cited in Mathur, p49). Charles G Morris "Emotion is a complex affective experience that involves diffuse physiological changes and can be expressed in characteristic behavior pattern. (as cited in Mangal, p314)

The analysis of above definition it can be said that Emotion is a state in which an individual is aroused or moved, it is a complex experience which is accompanied by physiological changes in the individual's body, and these emotions are expressed through individuals behavior. Moreover it involves many aspects viz. feelings, impulses and physiological reactions. Emotions are important aspect of a human life. The process of maturation and learning plays effective role in the development of emotions in human being. As the child grows, he may acquire various positive and negative emotions through his environmental experiences and training. Emotions and emotional behavior are the learned and acquired pattern of behavior. The individual from his childhood to adult attains maturity in terms of his physical and mental development; he also demonstrates adequate maturity in terms of his emotional development. Emotional Maturity is that characteristics of emotional behavior that is generally attained by an adult after expiry of his adolescence period. (Mangal, p320)

John D. Mayer and Peter Solovey "Emotional Intelligence may be defined as the capacity to reason with emotions in four areas: to perceive emotions, to integrate it in our thoughts, to understand it and to manage it." (as cited in Mangal, p325) Intelligence Quotient (IQ) was considered as the greatest predictors of success in all walks of life. But the researches conducted in 1990 onwards have revealed that a person's emotional intelligence measured through Emotional Quotient (EQ) may be a greater predictor of success than his or her IQ.

The B.Ed Students who are pursuing pre-service education. Will join as the teacher in our education system, should be emotionally intelligent, to handle the needs and demands of the society. As Karl Menninger says "What the teacher is, is more important than what he teaches"(as cited on <http://www.quotegarden.com>). He have been conferred with the responsibility of moulding the future of the child. "As Daniel Goleman developed the argument

that non-cognitive skills can matter as much as IQ for workplace success”(as cited on Wikipedia.org). “Emotional intelligence competencies are learned – and can be improved at any point in life. But first you have to be motivated – ask yourself if you really care. Then you need a well-structured learning situation where, for instance, you have a clear picture of what you want to improve, and can practice specific behaviors that will help you enhance the targeted competence.”(as cited on <http://danielgoleman.info>). If the teacher is emotionally intelligent or he develops his emotional intelligence in future, than he will be successful in his career.

Significance of the Study :

The present study tries to know about the Emotional Intelligence of B.Ed students. Through this study we can get idea about the emotional intelligence of both male and female B.Ed students.

Objectives :

1. To study the Emotional Intelligence of B.Ed students of Aurangabad City.
2. To compare the Emotional Intelligence of male and female B.Ed students of Aurangabad City.

Hypothesis :

1. The Emotional Intelligence of B.Ed students of Aurangabad City are high.
2. There is no significant difference in the Emotional Intelligence of male and female B.Ed students of Aurangabad City.

Method of Study: Survey Method was used for the study

Sample:

Out of the six College of Education two were selected at random and fifty students (25 boys and 25 girls) were selected at random from each selected college. The sample size is of 100 students.

Tool used for Study:

The Standardized tool, Roqan Emotional Intelligence test was used prepared by Prof Roquiya Zainuddin and Anjum Ahmed. It consists of thirty Items. The test covers five dimensions viz. Self Awareness, Self Regulation, Motivation, Empathy and Social Skills. (Roquiya and Anjum)

Procedure:

The Researcher administered the tool on students of his college and also visited one more college for data collection.

Scoring:

The scoring of the test is done by following the instruction given in the manual of the test. The Sum of Score in different dimension provides measures of Emotional Intelligence. Maximum score is 90 and Minimum Score is 30.

Analysis:

Mean, Standard Deviation and t-test was employed to analyse the data collected.

Table 1: Ranges of Raw scores of B.Ed Students on Emotional Intelligence Test

Score	Male	Female	Range
76 and Above	9	6	High
65-75	31	41	Normal
64 and Below	10	03	Low

Results :

The above table shows that majority of Male and female B.Ed students fall in Normal Range of EI, but more female falls in Normal Range as compared to Male B.Ed Students. Very few falls in High Range and Low Range, but male Male B.Ed Students falls more in High Range as compared to female B.Ed Students also Male B.Ed Students falls more in Low Range as compared to female B.Ed Students. So we can say that majority of the students Emotional Intelligence is in Normal Range.

Table 2: Mean, SD and t-test of scores of B.Ed Students on Emotional Intelligence Test

Sr. No.	Male		Female		Total		t-test	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Calculated Value	Table At .05 level
1	71.4	8.15	70.5	9.74	70.9	8.94	2.49	1.98

Results:

Table 2 shows the Mean, SD and t-test of scores of B.Ed students on Emotional Intelligence Test. The Male Mean (M=71.4) is less than female Mean (M=70.5) where as the boys SD (8.15) less than of girls SD (9.74). The t-test(df-98) calculated value is 2.49 where as the table value of t-test(df-98) is 1.98. The table value is less than calculated value this show that the difference is significant, therefore we reject the hypothesis. The Mean (M=71.4 and M=70.5 and Average – 70.9) also shows that the Emotional intelligence falls in the Normal Range. Therefore we can say that the Emotional Intelligence of B.Ed student is normal and we reject the hypothesis the Emotional Intelligence of B.Ed Student is High.

Conclusions:

1. The Emotional Intelligence of B.Ed student of Aurangabad City is Normal.
2. There is significant difference in Emotional Intelligence of Male and Female B.Ed students of Aurangabad City.

Suggestions :

1. The College of Education should provide the congenial environment for the development of Emotional Intelligence.
 2. The B.Ed students should be trained to manage their emotions as per the need and demand.
- At the end we can say that the B.Ed students should try to become Emotionally Intelligent because he who will be moulding the future generation.

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